

SOCIAL SCIENCES

CAUSES OF LANDSLIDES AND EROSIONS OCCURRING ON MOUNTAIN AND FOOTHILL SLOPES

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ABSTRACT

Analysis of the mechanism of landslide process should include the study of objective regularities of manifestation of a set of events leading to a decrease in slope stability and the occurrence of movement under the action of internal and external forces. It is rational to distinguish the stages of preparation, direct displacement and stability of landslides. Such a complex and multifactorial phenomenon as a landslide can be studied only if there is a detailed quantitative assessment of successive changes in the natural environment. In some cases, plastic landslides are the initial stage of landslides. They form on slopes or slopes composed of oily clays with a high colloidal content. These clays usually have a specific chemical and mineralogical composition (predominance of secondary mica and montmorillonite group minerals over other minerals). They are intensively weathered and become unstable with fluctuations in humidity and temperature

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Mountain and foothill landscapes are complex modified geosystems consisting of subsystems. One of the subsystems is the slope subsystem, where all erosion and landslide processes begin. In river subsystems, lateral and bottom erosion is a big disaster, which is accompanied by strong collapse of slopes and banks at scouring [1].

Due to their prevalence in Azerbaijan, landslide and erosion processes cause significant damage to the country's economy.

Landslide phenomena on slope lands of Azerbaijan are confined to clayey rocks of certain strategic horizons - from loess-like loams of Quaternary age to lithified clays of Middle Jurassic age. Landslides are most common in clayey rocks containing gypsum (swelling soils).

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In some cases, plastic landslides are the initial stage of landslides. They form on slopes or slopes composed of oily clays with a high colloidal content. These clays usually have a specific chemical and mineralogical composition (predominance of secondary mica and montmorillonite group minerals over other minerals). They are intensively weathered and become unstable with fluctuations in humidity and temperature [11].

When exposed as a result of natural processes or human activity, Lower Cretaceous and especially Jurassic mudstones and mudstone-like clays are subjected to active weathering. A thickness of loosened rock appears, in which changes in mineralogical composition occur with a noticeable increase in the amount of swelling minerals. The processes of swelling and shrinkage

are much more intensive. Shrinkage, flowing unevenly in the soil thickness, causes the appearance of a system of cracks with a specific orientation on slopes. They develop normal to the slope, but at some depth, depending on water yield of the soil and intensity of drying, they bend almost parallel to the surface. Repeated volumetric deformations during swelling-shrinkage may be the cause of slow sliding of the cover layers of clayey soils over the underlying rocks. However, the main role of these processes is to weaken the integrity of the massif by the fracture system and to separate the zone where significant moisture fluctuations occur. When the soil of the near-wall fracture zones is moistened, it soaks away, filling them with an unstructured liquefied mass. The rate of soaking depends on the initial moisture content, with a value found that is optimal for the process. As a rule, the fastest soaking occurs in the subsurface. Here, in an over-wetted soil, the strength drops particularly severely [3;5].

The impulse to initiate movement may be the occurrence of static water pressure that fills shrinkage and tension cracks. Usually a layer in which the moisture content, and consequently the soil viscosity and the rate of movement, is variable in depth and time, slides. Sometimes a zone at some depth moves faster. At the head and at the sides, areas of increased energy appear, and also here weathering begins to erode the exposed rocks. The local depression - the landslide bed - becomes an accumulator of groundwater and atmospheric water. Assuming that, all other things being equal, the first slope movement is due to a series of coincidences, the subsequent development of the landslide is naturally confined to the weakened area. Successive deformations lead to the formation of a bed, along which all new masses of soil moving from the head and side parts, as well as due to the capture of deeper layers by the weathering process, while the thickness of loosened masses covering them decreases. Significantly, the surface layer is usually passively entrained by the underlying, more mobile layer. As the landslide velocity varies from section to section and depends on the slope of

the bed, the relatively rigid surface crust undergoes failure and shifts, overturning [2;10].

The main signs of recognising landslides are the following: their shape (considerably elongated, pear-shaped), the state of soil in the gradient layer (the layer where the velocity changes from zero to maximum value is represented by overmoistened liquid-like soil), the nature and speed of movement (flow with velocities from millimetres to metres, sometimes tens and rarely hundreds of metres per day), direct dependence of activity and displacement rate on the amount of precipitation (displacement rates are especially high after heavy rains following a drought, or during thaws that replace severe frosts).

Landslide - sliding displacement of rocks down a slope either under the influence of gravity or under the influence of additional forces on these rocks. Violations of stability of slopes and slopes - a consequence of natural conditions: weather conditions, topographic and geological features of the slope, engineering and geological properties of rocks composing the thickness, groundwater regime, hydrological features of surface runoff on the slope, seismicity of the area, as well as human activity: watering of strata with leaks from utilities, undercutting the base of slopes during excavations, loading the top of the slope massive structures, embankments, vibration effects due to transport, hammering of the slope. The landslide can be triggered by studying the forms of landslide occurrence and knowing the natural environment. [6;8].

By investigating the forms of landslide occurrence and knowing the natural environment, it is possible to determine the cause of the landslide, and then provide the most effective landslide control measures.

As a result of movement of the landslide body, landslide steps, cracks, bulges, scarping and deformations of the base are formed on its surface.

The set of visual signs of landslide phenomena assessment can be divided into general, inherent in all types of slope stability disturbance, and partial, inherent in certain types of slope deformations. The general visual signs of assessment of landslide phenomena on slopes (slopes) include: significant steepness of the slope slope, the angle of inclination of which approaches or exceeds the critical angle of the soils composing the slope; appearance and development of cracks ("zakol") on the slope and its edge; characteristic washouts of the slope foot from the bank side; presence of landslide "circles", cracks, breaks, scarps, ledges and dumps on the slope; curvature of roads, paths, fences in the plan; cracks in buildings and structures standing near the slope edge; presence of filtration water outlets on the slope and formation of waterlogged areas in the slope depressions[7]. .

Private visual signs of landslide occurrences are usually characteristic of certain types of stability failures. Future landslides, i.e. sudden collapses of slopes and slopes in rocky and semi-rocky rocks and slumps, i.e. falling of individual stones and blocks of rock from a height, are usually indicated by: significant weathering and separation of rocks into blocks; presence of clay interlayers and their wetting; height, steepness and bareness of the slope; presence of rock piles from past

deformations. Scree movement will be indicated by the accumulation of fragmentary weathering products at the foot of steep slopes [12].

Cover slides, i.e. displacement of Quaternary sediments over bedrock, are indicated by tilted trees ("drunken forest"), telegraph poles, and skewed buildings. Splashing (local plate displacements of sandy and loamy soils) is characteristic of overwatered slopes in the places of filtration water outlet, at rapid lowering of water level in the reservoir, at dynamic impact on the moistened slope.

In assessing the stability of slopes composed of lithified clays, the behaviour of different weathered rock strata can be schematised by three computational models of discrete media mechanics:

- 1) a model of blocky structure (a fractureless medium, fracture-cracked rocks in isolation);
- 2) a model of a granular medium (crumbled material of fine crushed material, creating a strut when transferring loads, including from its own weight);
- 3) an elasto-viscous model capable of absorbing tensile forces (soil in which physical and chemical weathering has created cohesive forces, it is in such clay soils that landslides are formed).

Analysis of the mechanism of landslide development shows that at different stages of the process clayey soils in a landslide can be considered as bodies in calculation schemes: elastic - initial phase, formation of shrinkage and tension cracks; viscoplastic - initial stage of movement, when structural strength and initial shear resistance have a very significant effect; viscous - in formed flows at sufficiently large gradients, when the value of initial shear resistance can be neglected. Quite often within one landslide in different parts of the landslide (head, middle part and tongue, or in different layers in depth) soils behave as elastic, viscoplastic and viscous bodies.

The following landslide control measures are considered on landslide slopes [4;9].

1. Protection measures restricting human activity in the slope area: green belt - prohibition of forest cutting, uprooting and development of areas for vegetable gardens, destruction of shrubbery, grass cover; construction - establishment of the limit building boundary, type and weight of structures, demolition of existing structures, slowing down the pace of construction; earthworks - prohibition of any soil development in the passive zone - at the foot, loading of the slope in the active zone at the edge, increasing the slope steepness, opening unstable horizons of floating consistency; water management - prohibition of surface water drainage and irrigation, maintenance of drainage and drying devices, water supply and sewerage networks, patching of holes, cracks, establishment of safe levels and rates of water discharges washing the slopes; dynamic impacts - prohibition of blasting, pile driving, operation of vehicles.

2. Water drainage, drainage and drainage measures and devices are divided into surface devices and measures (terrain planning, crack sealing, pavements, bunding dams, upland and drainage channels, flumes, dripping springs); drainage devices (longitudinal and transverse cuts and galleries, drainage shafts,

absorbing wells and boreholes); isolation measures (various injection curtains, claying, freezing of soils).

3. Land management measures are aimed at unloading works in the active zone - complete removal of landslide masses, shearing of the active part of the landslide, cleaning of rock slopes, terracing and slope stabilisation, general slope leveling; loading in the passive zone - backfill and dumps; covering of rock slopes with nets; arrangement of stone traps.

4. Mechanical fixing of slopes consists in the arrangement of single anchoring elements in the form of piles of various types, passing through the landslide into the bedrock, or a series in the form of sheet pile walls, injection and permafrost curtains, etc. The mechanical fixing of slopes consists in the arrangement of single anchoring elements in the form of piles of various types, passing through the landslide into the bedrock.

5. The retaining structures are erected in the form of sheet pile walls (metal, reinforced concrete, wooden), retaining walls (stone, concrete, reinforced concrete), walls made of large diameter shell piles, as well as in the form of thrust shafts made of soil, rock piling.

6. Various types of injections (cementation, silicification, bituminisation, claying) are carried out to artificially compact and consolidate soils on the slope.

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